

live coding: sound – gesture – algorithm

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Extended Abstract

Text-based musical live coding (Collins et al, 2003) is approached from the notion of gesture as understood in embodied music cognition and sound-based composition such as to propose a framework for sound, movement and algorithms from a combined embodied-epistemic position. Live coding viewed as an extension of multi-scale studio based sound practices (Roads, 2015) for which human listening and machine listening (Collins, 2015; Van Nort, 2013) are the basis for intervention during the development process; yet positioned within the temporal framework of a performance. The programming language is an interface (Blackwell & Aaron, 2015) to a digital instrumental system that is understood as an epistemic tool (Magnusson, 2009) that presumes the potential of various forms of machine agency (Brown, 2016 & 2016b; Bown, 2009) and software agents (Whalley, 2009). The necessary formalism(s) of this digital system sets up the conditions for which human compositional and improvisational actions are complimentary: whatever aspects of the code that are not being improvised in the moment are composed/designed, be it by the performer-programmer(s), or by someone or some software prior. The code that is executed is both descriptive and prescriptive as a score (Magnusson, 2011), while presenting itself for further updates¹. Bricolage programming describes interactive process of writing and executing code, hearing the output, conceptualizing the next move, and so on, as outlined in the process of action and reaction (McLean & Wiggins, 2010). This understanding of live coding presents a distinct approach to the archetypal notion of sound-producing gesture as grounded in embodied music cognition research and developed in sound-based composition.

Gesture is a broad encompassing phenomena that can be approached from a number of different perspectives (Sha, 2002). A general framework of gesture can be understood to include the viewpoints of control, communication and metaphor (Godoy & Leman, 2010). In musical contexts, ‘gesture’ forms a central concept as expressions of our perception-action systems from which much musical meaning is formed (ibid.). From this embodied perspective a gesture is understood as: *multi-modal* in that it describes the audio and motor (movement) modalities independently; *multi-levelled* in that they include the dynamics of these modalities enacted through various sizes of spatio-temporal frames that may have a hierarchical or nested structure; and *monastic*, as gestures’ bridge the Cartesian mind-body division “appealing to our unconscious and conscious deployment of movement”. According to embodied music cognition (Leman, 2008) the body is a “mediator between the human mind and forms of the environment”, providing an “understanding of how the physical energy of music can be related to an ontology of action-oriented behavior”. This, action-oriented ontology (AOO) is grounded in perception and action being tightly coupled; that is, when phenomena are perceived there is a direct correlation to a corresponding action, a perception-action cycle (Godoy & Leman, 2008). Humans are not passive perceivers. This relates to the human tendency to attribute intent to agents/events, which occurs due to one’s ability to simulate the actions that carry this perceived intent (Leman 2008). This provides a way of understanding gesture as “patterns of embodiment” in terms of an awareness of one’s body in respect to the environment, or one’s ‘embodied imagination’ called the *body image*; and, as learned physical (human) motor patterns that require minimal or no mental effort to execute, often referred to as skill or *body schema*. Thus, gesture is understood as mental and corporeal phenomena (Godoy & Leman, 2008).

At the core of musical meaning is the sound-producing gesture. Prior to recording technologies, be they mechanical or electric, the concatenation and combination of various human sound-producing gesture was the only means for which music could come into being and holds particular emphasis in our understanding of what a performer is doing and how this relates to one’s AOO. A sound-producing gesture is the physical transfer of energy from the momentum of human physical movement to the resonating body of the instrument (ibid.). The experience of a live performer in acoustic and acoustic instrument modelled (Paine, 2009b) contexts presents the audience with an array of sound-producing gesture’s that will exist in one’s AOO or not.

¹ The visualization of code (Swift et al., 2013; McLean, 2010; Roberts, 2016)

While for the typical listener, much if not all, of what is perceived will be outside their AOO. The notion of gestural affordance confronts the aspect of musical perception for which listeners are able to render (complex) sound into body movement (regardless of training) as well as using “previously learned images of sound-related movement are projected onto sound” (Godoy & Leman, 2008). Of relevance here is *chunking* (ibid) for which continuous streams of sound and movement are ‘chunked’ into meaningful action-units, as well as the perceptual fusion of disparate action-sound units. The ‘chunks’ are understood as holistically perceived/conceived fragments of sound and action (Godoy, 2010). A related notion is that of goal-points, which are understood as “goal-postures in the form of the position and shape of the effectors (the hands in the case of gestures, but could also be the vocal apparatus in the case of vocal imitation) at certain important moments in the flow of musical sound, such as at downbeats or at various other accented events or at melodic, textural or timbral peaks.” (Godoy & Leman, 2008). Goal points can be understood in terms of keyframes, a notion from animation for which the most significant scenes and postures are drawn first – the keyframes, and then draw the interpolating frames or interframes that connect the keyframes. This understanding of goal-points provides intrinsic criteria for creating meaningful units by chunking continuous streams of sounds and gestures. (ibid).

This embodied understanding of sound-producing gesture provides a perceptual framework that has become an organizing/compositional and analysis framework for fixed media composition (Eigenfeldt & Basanta, 2010) that is exemplified in the work of Schaeffer and relates to his notion of ‘allure’ as described by (Maestri, 2017). Godoy (2006) extends Schaeffer’s iconic ‘sound object’ to ‘gestural-sonorous object’ noting the phenomenology of his approach was pointing to the more recent understanding of gestural affordance as understood in embodied music cognition and relating the typology of morphology of sound to corresponding gestures. The gestural understanding of sound relates to Smalley’s (1997) notion of gestural surrogacy that describes various degrees of perceptual awareness of the source through: *primal gesture* – that is gestures that sound-producing gestures are based; *first-order surrogacy*, that projects the primal gesture into sound that is pre-musical; *second-order surrogacy*, is traditional music gestures that reveal a level of musical skill; *third-order surrogacy*, describe gestures that are imagined yet the source cannot be known for sure; and *remote surrogacy*, which refers to unknown and unknowable sources as any human action behind the sound vanishes. Within the context of acousmatic music which Smalley is writing, he warns to be wary of technological listening that occurs when the “listener ‘perceives’ the technology or technique behind the music rather than the music itself” (ibid)². While this transparency of technology that Smalley promotes, may or may not be desired, it is precisely this type of technological listening that the live coder requires in the deployment of algorithms.

This embodied sound based perspective of gesture provides a conceptual framework for which specific algorithms can be associated to specific abstract typological and morphological sound-gesture descriptors. This in turn provides a gestural dimension to the temporal aspect of algorithms and codeomorphology (McLean & Wiggins, 2010), such that live coding can be understood to be the real-time composition of interactive algorithmic sound gestures requiring a cognitive framework grounded in embodiment and epistemic perspectives. This approach to gesture continues previous work by the author (Jarvis & Van Nort, 2018) in developing a posthuman notion of gesture human-machine agency as well as nonhuman forms of agency (Brown, 2016 & 2016b; Bown, 2009; Barad, 2007)

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² Smalley’s (1997) gesture - texture framework is relevant

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